

IMPLEMENTATION OF COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE IN PUBLIC PARTICIPATION-BASED WASTE MANAGEMENT IN PURWOSARI DISTRICT, PASURUAN REGENCY

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze The waste problem in Pasuruan Regency has reached a critical point due to the continued dominance of traditional approaches in waste management. This journal aims to analyze the implementation of collaborative governance in participation-based waste management through the Community Self-Help Group (KSM) program in Purwosari District, Pasuruan Regency. The approach used is descriptive qualitative with a case study in Purwosari Village. The results of the study indicate that collaboration between the government, KSM, and the community through the waste bank program, plastic recycling, and maggot (Black Soldier Fly) cultivation is able to reduce waste volume significantly. However, the level of community participation is still limited to 35% of residents, so that more inclusive strategic collaboration, strengthening regulations, and modernization of technology-based management system information are needed to improve the effectiveness of sustainable waste management.

Keywords: Collaborative Governance; Waste Management; Community Participation; KSM; Purwosari.

INTRODUCTION

Waste management is a serious challenge facing nearly every region in Indonesia, including Pasuruan Regency. The old paradigm of waste management, which focused solely on collection, transportation, and final disposal (3P), has proven incapable of addressing waste issues sustainably (Dr. Enri Damanhuri). As a result, landfills (TPA) continue to experience overcapacity, while public awareness and participation in waste reduction remain very low.

In Purwosari Village, Purwosari District, Pasuruan Regency, the waste problem is increasingly neglected. Based on BPS data (2019), from a total of 8,434 village residents, 17,964 m³ of waste is produced per day with a generation rate of 2.13 liters/person/day. Ironically, only 0.13% of this waste enters the TPS (landfill), while the remaining 99.87% is buried, dumped in vacant land, or burned. This condition demands a new, more participatory and collaborative approach to waste management. The concept of Collaborative Governance offers a governance framework that involves various government, community, and private sector stakeholders in the decision-making process and program implementation together. In the context of waste management, this

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approach is realized through Community Self-Help Groups (KSM) which act as agents of change at the community level. KSM seeks to encourage paradigm shifts, the adoption of new values, and institutionalizing them in the daily lives of the community (Mu'min Ma'ruf, 2017).

This journal aims to examine the application of collaborative governance in community participation-based waste management through the KSM program in Purwosari District, identify obstacles and opportunities for collaboration, and provide policy recommendations for strengthening sustainable waste governance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Collaborative Governance

Collaborative governance is a governance approach that integrates various actors from the public, private, and civil sectors in a collective decision-making process oriented towards the public interest. Ansell and Gash (2008) define collaborative governance as an arrangement in which one or more public institutions directly involve non-governmental stakeholders in a formal, context-oriented, and deliberative decision-making process.

In the context of waste management, collaborative governance requires active coordination between local governments (Environmental Services), community groups (KSM, Waste Banks), and individual citizens. Each actor brings different resources, knowledge, and legitimacy, making collaboration key to the success of an effective and sustainable waste management program.

Community Self-Help Groups (KSM)

Community Self-Help Groups (CBOs) are community organizations focused on poverty alleviation and community empowerment. CBOs act as bridges between government interests and the needs of grassroots communities. In waste management programs, CBOs serve as facilitators, organizers, and technical implementers of waste collection, sorting, recycling, and composting (Kusumastuti et al., 2021).

KSMs in Pasuruan Regency play a strategic role in supporting Pasuruan Regency Government policies, particularly the One Village Waste Bank (SDSB) program. KSMs' success is largely determined by the level of community involvement, village government support, and the availability of waste management infrastructure and technology.

Community Participation in Waste Management

Community participation is an essential component for the success of community-based waste management programs. According to Government Regulation No. 81 of 2012, district/city governments are required to develop a master plan for waste management that involves active community participation. This includes waste sorting at source, composting, recycling, and involvement in environmental education programs (Sari and Anggoro, 2020).

RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses a qualitative descriptive approach with a case study method. The research location is concentrated in Kacang Bayi Hamlet, Purwosari Village, Purwosari District, Pasuruan Regency, which has been one of the pilot areas for the implementation of the KSM waste management program since 2022. Primary data were obtained through field observations and in-depth interviews with KSM administrators, Environmental Agency officers, and residents involved in the program. Secondary data came from official documents, KSM activity reports, BPS data, and relevant previous research.

Data analysis was conducted thematically, identifying collaboration patterns, participation levels, implementation barriers, and the program's impact on the environment and community well-being. Data validity was ensured through source and method triangulation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Condition of Waste Management in Purwosari District

Waste management in Pasuruan Regency has relied on the traditional 3P approach (collection, transportation, and final storage). The increasing volume of waste, coupled with population growth, is not matched by adequate landfill capacity. The TPI BISA Waste Bank in Pagak Village, Beji District, is an innovative initiative that has successfully managed both organic and inorganic waste, even transforming it into economically valuable crafts. However, the reporting system is still manual, making it prone to errors and internal conflicts between managers (Rosadi et al., 2019).

In Purwosari Village, the potential economic value of managed waste ranges from Rp 2,786,138 to Rp 49,064,835. Waste composition includes biodegradable waste, plastic, metal, glass, paper, textiles, and hazardous and toxic waste. Unfortunately, limited infrastructure and low public awareness mean that most waste still ends up in incinerators or dumped in rivers (Octaviana and Hardianto, 2020).

Implementation of Collaborative Governance through the KSM Program

The Pasuruan Regency Government, through the Environmental Agency, is implementing a program to establish and mentor waste management cooperatives (KSMs) as a concrete manifestation of collaborative governance. This program integrates three main actors: the government as regulator and facilitator, KSMs as the driving force, and the community as implementers and beneficiaries.

In Kacang Bayi Hamlet, the KSM program has been running since 2022, with a monthly contribution of IDR 15,000 for households and IDR 40,000 for market vendors. Waste is collected, transported to the waste disposal site (TPS), and then further managed. The vendors' association is also involved by providing trash bins at each stall. The collaboration between KSM administrators, village youth, and residents reflects the spirit of mutual cooperation in community-based environmental management.

The plastic waste management program is implemented through the following stages: (1) outreach to village leaders and residents; (2) community service to clean the environment; and (3) sorting waste at the plastic waste bank to be processed into craft products with economic value (Supiatin and Maulida, 2019; Sari et al., 2023).

Organic Waste Management Innovation: Maggot Cultivation (BSF)

One of the most prominent innovations in the Purwosari KSM collaboration is the Black Soldier Fly (BSF) maggot cultivation program at Omah Maggot Warna Warni (OMWAWA). This program utilizes household organic waste as feed for BSF larvae. The process includes collecting organic waste, fermenting it with EM4 and molasses, hatching BSF eggs, rearing larvae in bioponds, and harvesting young maggots for animal feed and compost as organic fertilizer (Azizaendah et al., 2023).

This program not only reduces the volume of organic waste polluting the environment but also creates new economic value. Harvested young maggots can be used as feed for chickens, fish, birds, and ducks, while the kasgot provides high-quality organic fertilizer. The involvement of village youth in waste collection and maggot care strengthens the intergenerational collaboration in environmental governance.

Obstacles in Collaborative Governance of Waste Management

Although the KSM program has had a positive impact, several significant obstacles remain, hindering the optimization of collaborative governance. First, community participation remains low—only 35%, or approximately 20 of the 70 households in Kacang Bayi Hamlet, actively

participate in the program. Most residents who have not participated still throw garbage into the river or leave it on the roadside. Furthermore, pollution from industrial waste discharged into the river threatens the local aquatic ecosystem.

Second, the manual waste bank reporting system is prone to errors and internal conflicts. Modernizing the information technology (IT)-based system is urgently needed to improve transparency and accountability in management (Rosadi et al., 2019). Third, infrastructure constraints, such as waste collection vehicles and processing facilities, pose operational obstacles that contribute to program failure.

Impact of Collaborative Governance on the Environment and Society

The success of the KSM program within the Collaborative Governance framework has had multidimensional impacts. Environmentally, reducing the volume of waste going to landfills has had a positive impact on air, soil, and air quality around residential areas. Villages in Pasuruan Regency that have implemented community-based waste management have even achieved near-zero waste status and generated hundreds of millions of rupiah in Village Original Income (PAD) per month from waste management.

From a social perspective, this program fosters collective awareness and strengthens community ties through community service activities and community groups. Early waste management education in schools helps shape clean living and environmental stewardship in the younger generation (Sari and Anggoro, 2020). Economically, processing waste into recycled products and maggots opens up new business opportunities for KSM members and residents.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

The implementation of collaborative governance in community-based waste management in Purwosari District, Pasuruan Regency, has proven to produce more comprehensive and sustainable solutions than conventional approaches. Collaboration between the government (Environmental Agency), KSM (Citizens' Movement), and the community through waste bank programs, plastic recycling, and BSF maggot cultivation has had a positive impact on reducing waste volume, increasing environmental awareness, and creating new economic value.

However, there are several challenges that need to be overcome: (1) the low level of community participation, which has only reached 35%; (2) a manual reporting system that is prone to errors; and (3) limited waste management infrastructure. The success of collaborative governance requires commitment from all parties, clear regulations, and continuous technological innovation.

Suggestions

Based on the research findings, several policy recommendations are proposed as follows:

1. Modernization of information technology-based management systems to increase reporting transparency and operational efficiency of waste banks.
2. Intensify waste management education and outreach programs from school level to the general public to increase participation levels.
3. Strengthening waste management infrastructure and facilities (transport vehicles, recycling facilities, maggot bioponds) to support the KSM program's aspirations.
4. Providing incentives and rewards for citizens who actively participate as a motivation for community-based strategies.

5. Strengthening enforcement of waste management accompanied by strict sanctions for violators and the establishment of a cross-stakeholder collaboration forum.

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